

FINANCIAL LITERACY SKILLS LEVEL AMONG SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE BUSINESSES: LESSONS FOR ENTREPRENEURIAL DECISION-MAKING IN LAGOS, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Remarking on the strategic significance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprise (SMEs) as critical to any economy growth and employment creation opportunities, there are evidence that support the poor possession of the appropriate financial literacy skills and knowledge, required by SMEs to effectively make entrepreneurial decision, needed for business growth and the overall economic development. Previous studies on the *leitmotif* of financial literacy skills have largely been interrogated through the prism of financial institutions and as an indicator for gauging inclusion leaving sparse research attention to understand its implications on entrepreneurial decision making among SMEs. This research chasm provoked this study. The aim of this paper is therefore to dissect and understand the place of financial literacy skills and knowledge in entrepreneurial decision-making of SMEs. A total of 15 SMEs were recruited on purpose with the semi-structure interview type, used in eliciting qualitative data. A collection of different themes and sub-themes were identified with the application of the NVivo (v.12) qualitative software and analysed with the content qualitative analytical tool. Pattern and level of financial literacy include understanding of financial decision, management of money and implementation of financial decision. SMEs' financial literacy, required for effective entrepreneurial decision, includes knowledge on profitability, cash management skills and knowledge on investment with accompanied challenges, such as bad financial behaviour, financial irresponsibility and lack of basic education. The study makes a genuine case for the prioritization of the importance of financial literacy skills and knowledge for clear cut entrepreneurial decision-making and growth.

Keywords: Financial literacy, literacy, entrepreneurs, small business, decision-making, Nigeria.

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1. Introduction

The Nigerian economy, like other similar economies, is still largely characterized by the conundrums of poor economic indicators in the areas of unemployment, inflation and ease of doing business [1]. Several commentaries and policy frameworks have consistently suggested the growth and support of SMEs as the cornerstone to provoking solutions to any economic challenges [2]. Yet, SMEs with little or no financial literacy skills and knowledge unarguably will contribute sparsely to the economic growth of any nation [3]. The emphasis, however, is the contention for increased support for improved financial literacy knowledge of SMEs. The arguments on the significance of financial literacy have repeatedly been echoed as a necessary skill, needed for persons involved in the evaluation of complex financial decisions, especially in the entrepreneurial decision-making of SMEs. Financial literacy in the context of entrepreneurial decision-making explicates an entrepreneur's capability to comprehend and interpret financial information and decisions within a complex business situation. It extends to an entrepreneur's possession of skills and knowledge that are critical to the survival of the entrepreneurial venture in the areas, considered as potent to the growth and development of the business entity. Research evidence has shown the poor state of SMEs' financial literacy skills and knowledge with provoking impact on the effectiveness of entrepreneurial decisions and overall business success [4].

The different financial literacy skills and knowledge of SMEs for appropriate and effective entrepreneurial decisions are unconnected to the acquisition of skills in the arena of debt management skills, investment and saving knowledge, financial decision skill and knowledge and ability to prepare and manage cash flow transactions in the entrepreneurial business respectively [5]. Importantly, the array of these skills and knowledge has further reiterated the fundamentals of financial literacy skills in the quest for SMEs growth. However, the collection of challenges that have continued to constrain SMEs owners' acquisition of financial literacy skills and knowledge, needed for effective business decision and enterprise success, have continued to form public contention. For instance, financial literacy literature reports socio-economic factors, such as age and business occupation, others include poor financial behaviour and record keeping and accounting skills and lack of appropriate basic education for the comprehension of basic financial literacy skills [6]. The argument is how SMEs' business owners can upturn these challenges into appropriate and informed knowledge in order to make entrepreneurial decisions that can transform their business enterprise for good. The present study seeks to accentuate the importance of financial literature for SME for decrease in business failures. For instance, the study is position to provoke critical financial literacy understanding such that will expose SMEs to the nitty-gritty of financial literacy education and its importance for business survival and growth in the future. To be sure, the identified challenges and skills of financial literacy, reported in this study, can be argued as important metrics for averting business failures on the part of SMEs in the future. The pursuit of this goal with the present economic realities requires SMEs with adequate financial skills and knowledge that must be applied in their business endeavors to dwindle the ascending rate of business failures and support the growth of the economy in turn.

There are existing studies on financial literacy skills and knowledge in Nigeria ranging from the financial institutions to other establishments. For instance, [7] examined financial literacy and access with implication for women entrepreneurs; [8] analyse financial literacy and financial inclusion for the development of entrepreneurship in Nigeria; [9] interrogated the nexus between financial literacy and business performance of entrepreneurs. From the other context, [10, 11] dissect the importance of financial literacy for organizational development and performance. The argument, identified from this collection of studies, reflects that hardly has there been any study that seeks to interrogate the financial literacy skills as a lever for effective entrepreneurial decision making among SMEs business owners in Lagos, Nigeria. This locus clearly exudes the originality of this paper. The objectives of this paper are to understand the pattern and level of SMEs financial literacy skill; identify financial literacy, required by SMEs for effective entrepreneurial decision and assess the challenges of SMEs' financial literacy skills acquisition.

The main relevance of this paper is the quest to examine the discourse of financial literacy beyond the conventional themes of organizational performance and inclusion narratives to a more nuance issue of its implication for effective entrepreneurial decision-making among SMEs business owners in Nigeria. With the interrogation of this issue, it is possible to engender a more distinct and fresh analysis of financial literacy skills in the broad canon of management literature. This argument takes the posture that the analysis of SMEs portrays importance for a fuller comprehension of financial literacy skills for the overall success of SMEs. Studies in other climes have reported the implication of financial literacy on SMEs decision making. Amongst these studies include SMEs use of financial statements for decision making in Pakistan [12]; effects of financial literacy and investment on access to finance and investment decisions in small enterprises [13]; SMEs managers and financial literacy [14]. Having established the importance of financial literacy for SMEs decision-making from the prism of other context, the present study attempts to interrogate how financial literacy can be used as a lever for entrepreneurial decision-making in Nigeria, with specific focus on selected SMEs in Lagos State. After a clear conceptualization of the twin concepts of literacy and financial literacy, the paper review issues on the financial literacy skills of SMEs, needed for effective entrepreneurial decision making. In what follows, the paper highlights and discusses the range of financial literacy skills acquisition of SMEs. The methodology employed is clearly enunciated with NVivo (v.12) software identify themes and sub-themes from the qualitative data.

1. 2. Literature review

Literacy and financial literacy explained

The concept of literacy is ill-defined and embraced varied meanings. The definition of literacy has continued to evolve over time in response to demand for economic expansion and the progress in the measurement and evaluation of literacy in recent time [15]. While several efforts have been employed towards arriving at a common definition of literacy, research has shown that arriving at a single definition of literacy is almost not possible [6]. The concept of literacy is generally defined as an individual's ability to read and write [1]. This definition has resulted in the classification and distinction between literate individuals and those considered illiterate [2]. The conceptual clarification and meaning of literacy are context specific. Research has shown that there is the probability of having misinformed meanings and information if both concepts are forced into the same context [4]. Therefore, the concept of literacy and illiteracy are dependent on the nature and type of measurement employed.

Literacy is explained as a social interaction that comprised the reading and interpretation of text, and the communication of text to an audience [16]. Dissecting the information and ideals, learnt from the text, can afford the audience the opportunity to construct the text in diverse and specific ways. In other words, the role of the social interaction can help the audience understand the text in a more profound way [17]. The characterization of a literate is profoundly based on the most important feature of being able to read and write and being in possession of basic education [18]. The theoretical explanation of literacy as an individual quality and an answer to all forms of social ills has established its social importance as a sovereign catalyst for development and change.

Financial literacy in the context of entrepreneurial undertakings is an individual's ability to integrate knowledge and skills into making financial business decisions [19]. It is considered as the utilization and management of money for an extended financial planning by an entrepreneur [20]. It entails an entrepreneur's ability to exhibit a set of skills and abilities to exploit existing resources towards making effective entrepreneurial decision. [21] conceptualizes financial literacy as an entrepreneur's ability to use knowledge and skills to effectively execute financial resources. For this study, the concept of financial literacy is conceived as an essential entrepreneurial understanding and skills, required for making effective entrepreneurial decision. Financial literacy has been identified as a critical component of any entrepreneurial growth. For instance, an increase in financial literacy has been shown to improve the entrepreneurial decision-making of SMEs [22].

[4] theorize financial literacy as the possession of different financial skills and information by an entrepreneur for making informed decision about the use of money and the overall improvement of their enterprise. Several arguments have linked being financial literate to an individual's behaviour, habit and a range of other external factors (6; 21). This suffices to argue that being financial literate encompasses a blend of factors and not fixed on a particular factor. Entrepreneurs make different decisions on the strategic importance of their enterprise at different point in their entrepreneurial journey [14]. No doubt, these decisions have financial undertone. The need for entrepreneurs' financial skills acquisition is fundamental to the growing rate of entrepreneurship failure. Conclusively, the working definition for this paper conceives financial literacy as an entrepreneur's ability to manage financial and non-financial resources for effective entrepreneurial decision of the enterprise.

Financial literacy skills, required by small business owners for entrepreneurial decision

The conceptual understanding of financial literacy is argued as an entrepreneur's ability to obtain and handle financial resources effectively for best results towards the attainment of the short-term and long-term enterprise [21]. Therefore, the short-term and the long-term financial management skills must be clearly in place for an entrepreneur to effectively take appropriate financial decisions in the entrepreneurial journey. Talking about short-term skills, entrepreneurs must be conversant with profitability and cash flow financial management skills, while investment, financing and credit analysis skills are mandatory as long-term financial management skills [23]. Financial planning, accounting, book-keeping and financial analysis skills are crucial financial management skills that an entrepreneur must possess to effectively make appropriate entrepreneurial decisions on the finance of the enterprise [24].

Other commentaries have identified the significance and knowledge of cash book, inventory records and effective debt management as fundamental financial literacy skills, required from any entrepreneur for effective financial decision making [12, 4]. [25] study argued that record-keeping skills remain fundamental in enhancing SMEs businesses for personal evaluation of the growth of the business, particularly if the consultation of a financial expert cannot be afforded to interpret and advice on this function [21]. In other words, managers of small businesses need the knowledge of financial management skills for an explicit interpretation of bank statement and manage the finance of their businesses effectively.

Committing to wrong financial decision among small business owners is replete in the financial literacy literature [26]. The concept of financial training as a measure of addressing the financial literacy skills gap among small business owners can provoke more effectiveness when integrated with SMEs' daily activities. There is a consensus among financial literacy scholars that an increase in SMEs' business owners' level of financial literacy through training has the likelihood of increasing the effectiveness of entrepreneurial decision they make in their businesses [27]. In contrast, the lack of financial skills can engender problems for SMEs business owners. For instance, low understanding of financial literacy skills can prevent SMEs from adequately comprehending financial options for the growth of the enterprise [28, 29]. However, evidence of strong capacity building of SMEs business owners with respect to being able to prepare financial statement and other financial plans have positive feedback on the entrepreneurial decisions of the enterprise. The conclusion, drawn from the above commentaries, have been able to establish that SMEs business owners need short-term financial literacy skills to effectively manage their enterprise and make sound business decisions for business growth.

Financial literacy as discussed thus far needs to be applied and the lack thereof manifests in the dysfunctionality of the business. Business innovation amid global socio-economic and socio-political instability somehow disrupts business models that are crafted in ensuring growth, sustenance, and stability in the economy. [18] assert that a vast number of SMEs whose function and purpose is to contribute to the core economy of their respective countries have a desolate and insecure future unless they reengineer their products, processes, and business models. The business terrain has become complex and unpredictable, posing a plethora of questions on financial literacy, and what may be linked to it. Research on innovation and entrepreneurship attests to how complexity in the business environment may perform better using multiple collaborative actors [15]. Collaborative actors with resources must be available to ensure the functionality and sustainability of SMEs. Resources may range from (i) costing the business to crafting an astute, meaningful, and relevant business plan. In the strategic business plan, (ii) the narration and articulation of the available capital for the business to set the tone for the functionality and life of the business. Importantly, (iii) the execution of the business plan and continuity in updating the business plan based on the *status quo* of the business environment. In addition, (iv) a self-audit exercise to assess functionality and compliance to all statutory requirements pertaining to SMEs and the general running of a business.

Conundrums of SMEs financial literacy skills acquisition

The challenge of anxiety has been repeatedly reported in the financial literacy literature as critical to determining an entrepreneur's financial behavior, such as the management of money. For instance, [21] study established that the consequence of bad financial behaviour among entrepreneurs including spending above budget and earnings and exceeding the amount of credit, allowed for a specific period, are challenges of financial illiteracy among small business owners. In other words, when entrepreneurs possess these ranges of behaviour, it is likely they display financial irresponsibility in the management of the enterprise. [25] study shows that among other factors that explain the failure of SMEs entrepreneurs in terms of effective entrepreneurial decision are inadequate record keeping skills, poor accounting skills and the absence of appropriate control mechanism in the enterprise. The study concludes that the entire effect of poor financial record skills among SMEs business owners is the consequence of poor financial analysis. [26] examined the business knowledge of start-up entrepreneurs. The study found a wide range of financial illiteracy

among entrepreneurs with basic education and others without basic education. This research finding corroborated with existing commentaries on the significance of education for entrepreneurial success. In other words, the lack of it has been consistently sighted as a challenge to the acquisition of financial literacy skills [26].

[30] established the level of financial literacy among South African business start-ups. The study examined the role of socio-economic and demographic factors including age, gender and marital status as having significant effect on the financial literacy acquisition of start-up entrepreneurs. Disparity in age between entrepreneurs show more significant decline in the propensity to be financially literate among the entrepreneurs. A conclusion from this analysis explains that the more an individual progresses in age, the more the probability to be financially literate with a consequential effect on the financial and entrepreneurial decision of the enterprise [31]. [32] examined the awareness, knowledge and understanding of financial literacy concepts among selected entrepreneurs in South Africa. Findings show that many entrepreneurs demonstrated an inability to manage household budget and indifferent attitude towards spending. This explains entrepreneurs' poor knowledge and awareness of budget management skills with implications on the financial decision of the enterprise.

Among others, the poor financial literacy acquisition of entrepreneurs has continued to magnify with increasing number of business failures. This challenge is coupled with the poor ease of doing business and the retrogressive economic performance of Nigeria. Therefore, while entrepreneurial activities have been argued as the bedrock of any sustainable economy, canvassing measures to address the poor financial literacy skills among SMEs business owners remain fundamental to effective entrepreneurial decision-making for economic growth [21]. This argument is pursued in this study.

3. Research methodology

3. 1. Philosophical background

The philosophical enquiry guiding this study is borrowed from the assumptions of the interpretivist research philosophy. The assumption is reviewed to qualitatively understand financial literacy skills level among SMEs towards making effective entrepreneurial decisions. The interpretivist research philosophy affords the opportunity to unravel, understand and deduce how financial literacy can be employed to appropriating effective entrepreneurial decisions among SMEs owners. In other words, it allows for the integration of the human element in such a way by concentrating on the meanings emanating from a specific research situation and how these meanings can be qualitatively interpreted [33]. As with this study, the human elements of selected SMEs' owners were interviewed to be able to understand the meaning of financial literacy skills level and the implication for effective entrepreneurial decision. Therefore, the qualitative assumptions of the interpretivist approach support the intention of this study to qualitatively understand financial literacy skills level among SMEs and its ensuing implication for making appropriate business decisions.

3. 2. Design and study population

The study design is premised on the assumptions of the exploratory research design. The exploratory research design affords the opportunity to expand the limit of existing knowledge on SMEs financial literacy skills levels and the consequence for making entrepreneurial decisions [34]. For example, the exploration of existing studies on SMEs owners' financial literacy skills level reveals a research gap on financial literacy discourse with sparse research focus on the SMEs in Nigeria. To address this research gap, the assumption of the exploratory research design becomes crucial in order to further expand the financial literacy narrative through the lens of the largely neglected SMEs owners in Lagos, Nigeria. Selected SMEs business owners were recruited as the study population from the popular Oshodi Market in Lagos State, Nigeria. The characteristics of the population comprised SMEs in the agro-food business, traders, electronics and household equipment, furniture, transportation and other general merchandize. The identification and selection of these range of sample does not include any specific criteria, rather the level and nature

of interaction, employed in the study, affords a clear unpacking of the respondents' opinions, experiences and perception of the subject matter (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

3. 3. Research recruitment, instrument and data collection procedure

Respondents were recruited based on purposive and convenient sampling strategies. The first phase commenced with the initial identification of SMEs owners who are likely to participate in the study. To ensure that SMEs owners with the requisite knowledge on financial literacy were recruited for the study, referrals were obtained from the coordinator of shop owners. In turn, a total number of 20 respondents were identified and referred for the study. The researcher was only able to recruit and interview a total of 15 respondents as the study sample size. This was attained after careful screening of others who could not participate in the study as a result of the timing and nature of the study. This sample size in line with the appropriate sample size suitable for a qualitative study in the literature is justified to unravel deep research findings in a typical qualitative study of this nature [35].

The semi-structure interview approach was employed as the data collection instrument. This is justified to allow for the interrogation of supplementary questions and the uncovering of additional responses and ensure clarity in the circumstance that there are observed vagueness in the responses, supplied by the respondents [36]. The interview process employed an interview guide to control the flow of questions and the feedback responses [37]. The interview method of data collection was not isolated from known challenges including vagueness, ambiguity of feedbacks and the likelihood of misinterpreting the questions and responses respectively [37]. In this study, these challenges were addressed by structuring the interview questions in the official language of English since this is widely understood by the respondents. Similarly, the arrangement of the questions was worded in such a manner that a possible barrier of misinterpretation would be avoided. The interview was conducted face-to-face. The total duration of the interview culminated into two months (March 9, 2022- May 12, 2022). The entire interview procedure was recorded, and it was ensured, that additional notes were taken as back to unclear responses. The general questions, enquired from the respondents, reflected on the financial literacy skills level of SMEs business owners. The precise questions asked touched on the basic financial literacy skills of SMEs, required for making effective entrepreneurial decisions and the measures for addressing the financial literacy skills gap of SMEs business owners.

3. 4. Data quality and analysis

The reliability and quality of the qualitative data were strictly ensured by adapting the [38] four strategic approaches to determining the reliability of the qualitative data, such as the need for credibility, transferability of data, dependability and ensuring confirmability of data respectively. In this study, the credibility of the qualitative data was ascertained by ensuring that the data and results adequately reflected the opinions and perceptions of the respondents, shared during the interview. On transferability of data, it was ensured, that the results, obtained from the qualitative data, were transferable to another similar research context if replicated. The dependability of the research and data followed with ensuring that the data collection approach and the results all complied with appropriate ethical consideration including the protection of the anonymity of the respondents and the strict exclusion of vital information that can jeopardize the integrity of the respondents in whatsoever form. In addition, it ensured the secrecy of information by protecting the data from external intervention as a breach of secrecy.

Importantly, the consent of all respondents was adequately observed, and respondents were informed of their right to quit or refuse participating in the study at any point should they desire to do so. Lastly, confirmability was pursued to explicitly allow for the interaction between the data sets and the results of the study. The qualitative data were analysed from two stream of analysis. First, the NVivo (v.12) qualitative software was used to identify major themes and sub-themes from the transcribed data. Thereafter, the different themes and sub-themes were analysed with the content qualitative analytical tool. The analysis gave a deep insight into understanding the financial skill literacy requirement of SMEs owners and the appropriate measures, required for addressing

any inherent entrepreneurial decision-making challenges. The names and privacy of all the SMEs were concealed on ethical grounds. The limitations of the study were identified in the area of delayed access to interview some of the SMEs owners. **Table 1** shows the research questions in sync with the different themes and sub-themes.

Table 1

Emergence of Themes and Sub-themes from the NVivo Analysis

Research questions	Major themes	Sub-themes
What are the patterns and level of SMEs financial literacy skill and knowledge?	Acknowledgement and understanding of financial decisions; understanding about the management of money; planning and implementation of financial decisions and processing of financial information	Inventory accounts knowledge and management; debt management skills; financial transaction skills and book-keeping knowledge
What are the financial literacy skills, required by SMEs for effective entrepreneurial decision?	Financial literacy knowledge on profitability; financial knowledge on cash management skills; financial literacy knowledge on investment; financing and credit analysis skills	Cash flow knowledge; financial knowledge of business; financial planning skills and financial resourcefulness
What are the financial literacy skills challenges affecting SMEs entrepreneurial decisions?	Bad financial behavior, such as spending above budgets and earnings; financial irresponsibility in the management of the enterprise; poor record keeping and accounting skills and lack of basic education	Bad management of household budgets; socio-economic constraints; poor control mechanism and financial literacy education constraints

Source: NVivo Analysis

4. Data analysis and interpretation of results

4. 1. Patterns and level of SMEs financial literacy skill and knowledge

The discourse of financial literacy skill has continued to raise concern among SMEs' owners with the increasing rate of small business failure. Although, several factors have been identified as constraints to business failures, the theme of financial literacy skill remains predominant as many SMEs' owners often neglect the fundamental significance of possessing financial literacy skills. The different arguments, shared by most of the respondents interviewed, clearly shows that most SMEs possess basic financial literacy knowledge, such as the acknowledgement and understanding of making financial decisions for their enterprise, the understanding and management of money, especially in relation to the management of the enterprise, debt management and financial transaction skills, the ability to plan and implement financial decisions. For instance, it was narrated, that whilst these skills are evident in several SMEs, the larger constituents of SMEs only possess basic financial literacy knowledge that has to do with business transactions, while lacking in financial planning, implementation and the good sense of financial decisions.

Unarguably, the importance of financial literacy skills is way beyond the knowledge of financial numeracy or an individual's ability to recognize financial transaction. It was collectively argued, that what seems to be the missing link is the sparse knowledge on making informed financial decisions that translate to how informed financial management of budget and investment knowledge can be made. One of the SMEs owners recounts the following submission.

I am sure one of the financial literacy skills patterns common among SMEs is the knowledge about the understanding and management of money. As an entrepreneur who deals with raking risk, being able to manage money in their enterprise is important for making appropriate entrepreneurial decisions and for the growth of the business. So, being able to manage money represents one of the levels of financial literacy knowledge as an entrepreneur, since we deal with money transaction in the entrepreneurship venture.

The possession of financial information represents an important component of being financially literate as it affords one the opportunity to make explicit business decisions based on the available financial information and the ability to process them. One of the respondents, explained that the possession of financial information has been a major factor to contend with as far as the need to be financially literate is concerned. For instance, it was argued, that possession of the

appropriate financial information has assisted him in making informed business decisions for the growth of his enterprise.

I think one pattern we should also try to comment on is the possession of financial information. Many of the SMEs do not understand the importance of being financially literate, informed and equipping oneself with the right mix of financial literacy information. For me, I think being financially literate, informed makes the difference in the life of an entrepreneur. We cannot be talking about financial literacy skill without talking about what financial information is available to possess.

Other sentiments, shared on the pattern and level of SMEs owners' financial literacy knowledge, reflect on planning and implementation of financial decision skills. This narration was supported by most of the respondents. For instance, it was argued, that planning and implementation of financial decision skills should be the basis of any financial literacy knowledge for entrepreneurs in their day-to-day business activities. In their opinion, while the knowledge and management of money depict a critical component of financial literacy skills for entrepreneurs, being able to plan and implement decisions that have to do with finance also represent a crucial part of an entrepreneurial success. One of the respondents argued thus:

We should also endeavor to talk about planning and implementation of financial decision skills. The pattern and level of financial literacy of many entrepreneurs can also be looked at through the prism of planning and implementation of financial decisions. It is not only sufficient to understand how money can be managed by an entrepreneur, but more importantly is the planning and implementation of financial decisions. So, for me, the pattern and level of financial literacy skill of entrepreneurs can also be linked to planning and implementation of financial decisions in the business venture.

4. 2. Essentials of financial literacy skills for entrepreneurial decision

The general argument on the essential financial literacy skills, required for making effective entrepreneurial decisions, reflects on the SMEs owners' need to possess financial literacy knowledge on profitability, financial literacy knowledge on cash management skills, financial literacy knowledge on investment and financing and credit analysis skills respectively. Several of the arguments were predicated on the need for SMEs to inculcate appropriate financial literacy knowledge towards addressing the many global changes. The world has been witnessing an increasing economic change globally with consequences for the survival of SMEs across the globe. Importantly, while the impact of these changes continued to impact SMEs growth, many of the respondents argued that possessing the appropriate and essential financial literacy can afford any SMEs to survive these economic tides. For instance, the importance of financial literacy knowledge on profitability cannot be over-emphasized.

Other sentiments were premised on the economic implication of entrepreneurs going out of business as a result of their lack of financial literacy knowledge on profitability including unemployment and economic hardship for members of the family and other dependents. Therefore, it was collectively agreed, that financial literacy knowledge on profitability remains important as it affords the business owner the opportunity to expand and take appropriate entrepreneurial decisions in the long run. One of the respondents explained:

This knowledge is essential and needed for an entrepreneur to make informed entrepreneurial decisions and remain in business. No business venture can go, if possible, without having the financial literacy skill on how to maximize profits from the business. In other words, profit is required for continuity and the cessation means the disruption or liquidation of such business. I will say taking oneself through the acquisition of financial literacy knowledge on profit is a necessity for any entrepreneurs in this part of the world.

Another perspective, shared on the essential financial literacy skill, required for effective entrepreneurial decisions, reflects the importance of financial knowledge on cash management skills. Again, this position clearly exudes that being financially literate without the appropriate skills of cash management can jeopardize the effective running of an enterprise. Thus, the contention, pursued in this paper, is the need for SMEs to robustly imbibe financial literacy on cash

management skills. Cash management skills afford not just the continuity of the business, but more precisely engender the expansion and growth of any business venture. In other words, the effective management of cash will position SMEs to plan by being able to avert any business risk with potential liquidation effect on the business. One of the essentials of financial literacy cash management skills was re-echoed below:

I can tell you that being financially literate with appropriate knowledge on cash management skills is crucial for the success of any enterprise. Many SMEs are not in tandem with the reality of how cash should be managed. If you want to remain in business for a long period of time, then there is a need to have a grasp of cash management skill as this is important to make future prediction among the business and plan in times of financial crisis. In essence, being able to manage cash will give room for business continuity even when the times are hard.

The global economic changes have incapacitated the operation and production of many SMEs leaving them with liquidation. The argument that follows from this analysis is the integration of financial literacy knowledge on investment for survival in this turbulent economic era. This means that SMEs must learn the tricks and modalities of investing by setting aside some portion of the profit from their business to cushion the effect of the growing economic disruptions and as a way of preparing for uncertain economic times. As argued, this must be learned through the ropes of financial literacy as being literate about the importance of investment does not occur without the need to seek for such knowledge. An SME merchandize reports as follows:

We are in a period of economic uncertainties and many challenges are befalling small businesses across the globe. Many of these challenges are affecting the entrepreneurial decisions and performance of SMEs. In my opinion, what I think is important at this time is the need for SMEs to acquire investment based financial literacy knowledge. This is important as it will equip them for any uncertainties and make appropriate entrepreneurial decisions for their businesses.

4. 3. Financial literacy skills challenges of SMEs

The management of SMEs financial literacy skills challenges constitutes an important component part of making informed entrepreneurial decisions and performance of an enterprise. Several challenges in terms of financial literacy, however, abound with consequence on the performance of SMEs. For this study, a number of these challenges include small business owners' bad financial behaviour of spending budgets and earnings, financial irresponsibility in the management of the enterprise, poor record keeping and accounting skills and lack of basic education among other constraints. These challenges, as argued by the large constituent of the SMEs, continued to hamper the business decision and performance of many SMEs. For instance, despite the possession of business acumen on the part of many SMEs, it was argued, that the challenges of financial literacy skills remain critical to the development of many SMEs. In other words, the basis of record keeping and accounting skills remains an issue for SMEs' business growth. One of the respondents who lent his voice to the challenge of poor record keeping and accounting skills recounted as follows:

I think I must comment on the challenge of poor record keeping and accounting skills. In my understanding I will argue that this has remained one of the major financial literacy skill challenges for many SMES. For instance, we understand that indigenous SMEs such as those that emerge from the Igbo traditional trade system where taught the essentials of small business through the apprenticeship system. Unfortunately, the large number of these apprentices who eventually start small businesses is found to lack the basis of record keeping and accounting skills.

Another financial literacy skill challenge of SMEs reflects the SMEs' owners' bad financial behavior, which includes spending above budgets and earnings on the part of many SMEs. For instance, it was contended, that many SMEs lack the appropriate budget skills, required for the management of their enterprise and other personal expenditures culminating in spending above earnings and profit. This argument is a pointer to the critical factor accountable for many SMEs' failures where budget, profits and expenditures are not aligning with the consequence of bad financial decisions for the business and ultimate business failure as it were. This analysis depicts the workings and structure of many SMEs operators in Nigeria with evidence of the lack of appropriate

budgeting and expenditure financial literacy skill knowledge. One of the SMEs speaks in the direction of how the challenge of bad financial behavior has liquidated many promising SMEs.

We need to talk about how some SMEs are operating without appropriate budgeting and planning knowledge. Majority of the SMEs do not have the requisite financial literacy skill on budget, expenditure and the management of profits. We have seen how many promising businesses collapsed due to the lack of financial literacy, planning and budget knowledge. Many of them result into bad financial behaviour and ended up spending above their budgets and earnings. Appropriate financial literacy knowledge of budgeting is clearly important for any SMEs to make effective business decisions.

The absence of basic education cannot afford SMEs to be knowledgeable on the intricacies and importance of financial literacy skills and its application to their business enterprise. The respondents also argued for the need for SMEs to religiously engage in the acquisition of basic education in order to provoke a nuance understanding of financial literacy skills. The argument pursued is the emphasis on ensuring that the structural impediments constraining the possession of adults' basic education on the part of SMEs are genuinely addressed through appropriate policy actions as a way of encouraging SMEs enrolment. With this in sight, SMEs can be more knowledgeable and oriented in financial literacy skill for the management of their enterprise and entrepreneurial decision-making. A SMEs business owner explained as follows:

It is no gainsaying, that many SMEs are deficient in basic education. With this, it is evident, that the acquisition of financial literacy skill will suffer some challenges. In my view, one thing that qualifies anyone to be financially literate is to have basic education, without which it becomes difficult to have financial literacy knowledge. Basic education remains pivotal to the management of the financial transaction of any business. As a result, many SMEs often liquidate with the owners' lacking in the requisite education to manage the financial transaction of the enterprise and make informed business decisions. **Fig. 1** summarizes the different themes and sub-themes.

Word Cloud

Fig. 1. Word Cloud depicting Themes and Sub-Themes

5. Discussion

The need to understand the financial literacy level of SMEs necessitates from the ascending rate of business failure, especially among start-up SMEs. Although, many SMEs' owners possess basic financial transaction knowledge, however, the importance and application of financial literacy knowledge and skill have been greatly downplayed by most SMEs' owners in their everyday business transaction. The findings show different patterns and levels of financial literacy skill including acknowledgement and understanding of the management of money, skills related to planning and implementation of financial decisions and processing of financial information. SMEs contribute significantly towards the development of the economy by creating employment opportunities. The results show that the capacity to continually create employment and remain in business cannot be unconnected with SMEs' ability to display a reasonable amount of financial

literacy skill and knowledge. These contestations have been rehearsed in similar literature (Singh, Sarva & Sharma, 2020; Egbo et al., 2020).

On the question of financial literacy skill and knowledge, required for effective SMEs entrepreneurial decisions, the study demonstrated a collection of important financial literacy skills mandatory for SMEs entrepreneurial decisions including financial literacy knowledge on profitability, financial knowledge on cash management skills, financial literacy knowledge on investment and financial and credit analysis skill. The fallouts from the global economy and the rising economic disruptions have affected SMEs in several ways. The onus for SMEs survival through effective implementation of entrepreneurial decisions cannot be overemphasized. For instance, one of these changes was the economic disruptions of the COVID-19 pandemic on SMEs. Thus, the possession of the relevant financial literacy skill and knowledge may assist SMEs overcome the daunting challenges of the economic downturn. In other words, financial literacy skills and knowledge emphasize the capacity to build and harness business connections for business growth. Existing studies explain similar financial literacy skill, required for SMEs' financial growth (Akhtar & Liu, 2018; Amari & Jarboui, 2017).

The findings also highlight several financial literacy skill challenges constraining SMEs effective entrepreneurial decision making including bad financial behaviour, financial recklessness in the management of the enterprise, poor record keeping and accounting skill and lack of basic education. These findings indicate that SMEs are still grappling with the intricacies of financial literacy skills in the running of their ventures. The current economic reality of Nigeria is no doubt structurally deficient for SMEs survival. Thus, SMEs, constrained by financial literacy skills, will hardly survive in the present economic conditions. Similar studies on SMEs financial literacy skill have found seamless measures for addressing these challenges (Garg & Singh, 2018; Singh, Sarva & Sharma, 2020). For instance, appropriate and strategic policy initiation will be of significant impact in addressing SMEs' owners' financial literacy challenges. The strategic policy should not only consider supporting SMEs, but more importantly should ensure that SMEs' owners play a key role through the acquisition of basic education and how this can be extended to the acquisition and utility of financial literacy skill in the interest of making effective business decisions. The methodology was limited in the number of accessible respondents and the time frame, required to complete the study. However, the sample size gives a good representation. Further study can be interrogated with a mixed research approach to understudy divergent or convergent of results.

6. Conclusion

There is no doubt that SMEs are important employment creation hub. Therefore, the significance of financial skill for effective planning and implementation of financial decisions forms a component part of successful SMEs businesses. Given that the acquisition of financial literacy skills and knowledge are not given the desired attention for business success in this part of the world, the study sought to interrogate the different pattern of financial literacy skills and required financial literacy skills and knowledge essentials for making appropriate entrepreneurial decisions among SMEs. However, to have a fuller grasp of these issues, the various financial literacy challenges affecting SMEs entrepreneurial decision-making were also attempted. On this premise, it is important to provoke a discussion on how the challenges of SMEs acquisition of financial literacy can be addressed, thereby clearly positioning SMEs on the path of economic sustainability and growth. In other words, SMEs' owners with low financial literacy knowledge can begin to attract financial insight on the management of their finances and business. While the intention to address these challenges, no doubt, remains positive, the low level of basic education among SMEs owners portends the possibility likely to hinder the progress of any policy, engendered for addressing financial literacy challenges.

Above all, the study makes a case for genuine efforts from all stakeholders in prioritizing the importance of financial literacy skill and knowledge for SMEs growth, especially in the area of sensitization and promulgation of a policy that can aid in putting this important sector on the part of development through financial literacy skill and knowledge acquisition. In addition, SMEs must be willing to embark on self-financial literacy education and must be willing to transmute the same

in making entrepreneurial decisions and other financial transactions. Future research can attempt a comparison of the financial literacy skill and knowledge of SMEs' owners from two or more sectors of the Nigerian economy. As it is, the current study is limited to a single case analysis of SMEs.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data cannot be made available for reasons disclosed in the data availability statement

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